

ASTRONOMY

TRACERS OF DISCS AND WINDS AROUND A HIGH-MASS YOUNG STAR (MWC297)

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Abstract

This article is presented a new catalog of 108 Herbig Ae/Be candidate stars identified in the Pico dos Dias Survey, together with 19 previously known candidates and four objects selected from the IRAS Faint Source Catalog. These 131 stars were observed with low and or medium-resolution spectroscopy, and complemented these data with high-resolution spectra of 39 stars. The objects present a great variety of $H\alpha$ line profiles and were separated according to them. As is known that most of the time a Herbig Ae/Be star presents a double peak $H\alpha$ line profile. Correlations among different physical parameters, such as spectral type and $v \sin i$ with $H\alpha$ line profiles were searched. We found no correlation among $H\alpha$ line profiles and spectral type or $v \sin i$ except for stars with P Cyg-ni profiles, where there is a correlation with $v \sin i$. In this work also used preliminary spectral energy distributions to seek for any influence of the circumstellar medium in the $H\alpha$ line profiles. The presence of [O I] and [S II] forbidden lines is used together with the $H\alpha$ line profiles and these preliminary spectral energy distributions to discuss the circumstellar environment of the Herbig Ae/Be candidates. The distribution of the detected [OI] and [S II] forbidden lines among different spectral types points to a significantly higher occurrence of these lines among B stars, whereas the distribution among different $H\alpha$ profile types indicates that forbidden lines are evenly distributed among each $H\alpha$ line-profile type. Combining the distance estimates of the Herbig candidates with the knowledge of the interstellar medium distribution, we have found that 84 candidates can be associated with some of the more conspicuous SFRs, being in the right direction and at a compatible distance.

Keywords: catalogs-circumstellar matter, clouds stars, pre-main-sequence, spectroscopic.

Characterized by their transitional nature, Herbig Ae/Be stars occupy a pivotal role in the study of stellar evolution. These young, pre-main-sequence stars exhibit spectral characteristics that place them between T Tauri stars and classical Be stars, thus providing valuable insights into stellar development processes. Typically located in star-forming regions, Herbig Ae/Be stars are surrounded by protoplanetary disks, which play a crucial role in their growth and subsequent evolution. The presence of these disks not only facilitates the accumulation of mass but also gives rise to complex interactions with stellar winds, influencing both the physical structure of the disk and the stars evolutionary path. Focusing on the role of disk and wind interactions, these processes are essential in shaping the characteristics and behaviors of Herbig Ae/Be stars. Stellar winds, which consist of streams of charged particles emitted by the star, can significantly impact the surrounding disk dynamics. As the wind interacts with the disk material, it generates shocks and instabilities, leading to enhanced mass loss and angular momentum transfer. This interplay not only affects the star's growth but also contributes to the dispersal of the surrounding material, potentially allowing for the formation of new planetary bodies. Understanding these interactions is crucial in creating a comprehensive picture of Herbig Ae/Be star evolution, particularly within groups such as MWC 297. Research on these phenomena reveals that the dynamics at play can vary substantially based on environmental conditions and individual stellar properties. By studying MWC 297, - insights into the broader processes governing young stellar systems and the even-

tual transition to main-sequence stars, ultimately refining our knowledge of stellar lifecycle stages and the formation of planetary systems.

Ever since the identification of the Herbig Ae/Be stars (HAeBes; Herbig, 1960) as a class of early-type pre-main sequence objects (Strom et al., 1972), these stars have taken centre-stage in star and planet formation studies. They have masses which place them in the transitional regime between Solar-type stars and high-mass stars. In detail, the change in star formation character between the high- and low-mass stars is the dichotomy between clustered and isolated formation, between boundary layer accretion and magnetospheric accretion, radiative and convective stellar interiors and between fast and slow rotation. Moreover, the discs around Herbig stars are in general brighter than around their low-mass counterparts, the T-Tauri stars. Therefore HAeBes are prime laboratories in which to study the evolution from actively accreting discs towards debris discs and mature planetary system.

1. spectral type A or earlier, with emission lines;
2. located in an obscured region;
3. fairly bright nebulosity in its immediate vicinity;
4. present an anomalous extinction law;
5. show infrared excess;
6. be photometrically variable; and
7. display line profiles of Mg II ($\lambda 2800$) in emission.

The first three tips were proposed by Herbig (1960) to define pre-main-sequence (PMS) stars of intermediate mass. The last four are an extension proposed by The' et al. (1994) to encompass the large set of new candidates. However, very few stars satisfy all

of them. One possible explanation is that the Herbig Ae/Be group spans a large range of evolutionary stages (Malfait et al. 1998).

Forbidden lines such as [O I] ($\lambda 6300$ and $\lambda 6364$) and [S II] ($\lambda 6716/ \lambda 6731$) trace the emission from low-density regions near the stars. The shape of the forbidden-line profiles can indicate the presence of disks or outflow characteristics. When a disk exists, these lines are expected to be blueshifted and asymmetric, as in T Tauri stars (TTSs) (Finkenzeller 1985), since the receding part of the outflow will be hidden by the disk. In HAeBe stars there is still a debate on the origin of the observed forbidden lines. Almost all observed [O I] lines are symmetric, and some authors (Bohm & Catala 1994) favor the idea of an origin in a spherically symmetric wind without the presence of disks.

Using the IRAS Point Source Catalog, TTS was based on dust properties and not on the star itself, selected criteria also included HAeBe stars. It is more difficult to be certain of the classification of a HAeBe star than of a TTS, because there is no feature like the Li ($\lambda 6707$) line as a clear signature of this class of objects.

Overview of MWC 297 and its significance in stellar formation studies

Located in the northern constellation of Cassiopeia, MWC 297 is pivotal in the study of stellar formation, particularly as a Herbig Be star showcasing both disk and wind processes. Its classification reflects a complex interplay of accretion and winds that influence the surrounding circumstellar environment. As noted, MWC 297s accretion rates and stellar parameters have implications that extend our understanding of the evolution of massive stars, with recent analyses revealing evidence for intense inner-disk photoevaporation in sources like MWC 297, significant for stars above (Vioque et al). Furthermore, the exploration of such stars enhances statistical studies into the accretion properties of Herbig Ae/Be stars, enabling researchers to hypothesize about the mechanisms of disk dissipation and the interaction between stellar and circumstellar material. Thus, MWC 297 serves as an essential case study for illuminating the processes that govern early stellar evolution.

Disk Processes in MWC 297

The study of disk processes in MWC 297 reveals crucial insights into the interactions between star formation and the surrounding circumstellar environment.

Observations suggest that intense Herbig Be stars like MWC 297 exhibit significant near-infrared excess, indicative of a robust inner disk structure that strongly influences accretion dynamics. This aligns with the findings regarding early HBe stars, which demonstrate high H α emission and active circumstellar environments, suggesting a complex interplay of material dynamics and star activity. Moreover, the detection of complex molecules and elements near young stellar objects in turbulent regions, such as those surrounding SgrA*, highlights similar disk processes potentially at work in MWC 297. These processes not only facilitate star formation but also influence subsequent evolutionary pathways, as evidenced by the relationship between dense circumstellar environments and the eventual dispersal of protoplanetary disks. Understanding the nuanced role of these disk processes is essential for comprehending the evolution of young star groups like MWC 297.

Wind Processes in MWC 297

Understanding wind processes in MWC 297 reveals critical interactions between stellar outflows and surrounding material. Winds play a significant role in shaping the protoplanetary disks accompanying young stars, influencing both mass loss and accretion rates. As demonstrated in recent studies, the characteristics of these winds can be correlated with the stellar properties such as effective temperature and luminosity, affecting the evolution of the disk itself. (Ji Yeon Seok et al., p. 291-291) highlights how the photodissociation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) varies with stellar temperature, suggesting that energetic radiation in MWC 297 leads to selective destruction of smaller PAHs. This process has implications not only for chemical composition but also for the dynamics within the disk. Furthermore, (J. Guzmán-Díaz et al., p. 182-182) indicates that transitional disk structures are often observed in young stars like MWC 297, underscoring how wind processes can contribute to the formation and dissipation of these disks, thus shedding light on the disk evolution in the context of wind interactions.

All eight of the main targets are known massive YSOs or Herbig Ae/Be stars. Some basic properties of these are given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Object	Distance (kpc)	Spectral type	Luminosity ($L_{\odot}$)	A_V (mag)	v_{LSR} (km s ⁻¹)
BD+40°4124/V1685 Cyg	$\sim 1^1$	B3V ²		3.1 ³	$\sim 8^5$
GL 490	$\sim 1^6$		2000 ⁶	42 ⁷	-14^9
M17SW IRS1	1.3/2.1 ¹⁴	O9V ¹⁵		17 ¹⁶	$\sim 17^{17}$
M8E	1.25 ¹⁰		20000 ¹¹	39 ⁸	~ 11 13
MWC 297	0.25 ¹⁸	B1.5V ¹⁸		8 ¹⁸	2 – 20 ¹⁸
MWC 349A	1.7 ²²		60000 ²³	9 ²³	10 ²⁵
S106	0.5–1.7 ²⁶	O7.5V ²⁶		13.6 ²⁷	$\sim 5^{29}$
VV Ser	0.2–0.6 ³⁰	B6V ² /B9V ³¹		$\sim 3^{31}$	$\sim 10^{33}$

All the sources are sufficiently compact that they could be observed by nodding the telescope such that the sources remained on the slit (the measured beam

separation is 22 arcsec). In addition to target observations, this approach uses standard stars to offer crude flux calibration and adjust for atmospheric absorption

features. The standard stars were chosen to have a range of spectral type from G6V through to O9V. This provided enough range to enable us to correct for the observed Brackett line absorption in the standards themselves. Cooler stars were not used since they have many

other spectral features in the wavelength ranges observed, and in practice we used the hottest standard available for any target. The Brackett line absorption in the standard was interpolated over to remove it.

Figure 1. Br γ (solid line) and Br12 (dashed line) line profiles after continuum subtraction, and correction for extinction.

The source's bias is debatable. Drew et al. (1997) found that a near edge-on inclination is necessary to explain the reported optical absorption line data, since otherwise the star would be near break-up velocity. Interferometry data is best modeled with a near-face-on orientation. An edge-on model may result in double-peaked line profiles if an ionized disc contributes. To align with previous studies, we use interferometric data to determine inclinations for this object. Murdoch & Drew's (1994) Br α /Br γ ratio is comparable to the Br γ /Br12 ratio of BD+40°4124 or M17SW IRS1, as seen in Figure 1. (Lumsden et al.2012) measured line widths are consistent with Drew et al.'s (1997) Br α width. Although Br12 has a similar FWZI to H α , Drew et al. found that H α has a greater FWHM. The Fe II profile does not feature the same broad wings. Most published MWC 297 spectra have symmetric Brackett line characteristics. Malbet et al. (2007) found that Br γ exhibits blueshifted asymmetric self-absorption. The greater spectral resolution data published by Murdoch & Drew (1994) and Weigelt et al. (2011) do not reveal this, implying that variability exists. The 1.083 μ m 2³S-2³P He I line (Drew et al. 1997) shows a P-Cyg-ni effect, indicating the presence of a wind. For a face-on

orientation, this wind might be polar or disc-shaped with a wide opening angle.

Drew et al. give a 5 GHz radio map revealing resolved radio emission from this source on the size of ~ 50 au. Both Malbet et al. and Weigelt et al. interferometry demonstrate the core Br γ emission is more extended than the K-band continuous light. Weigelt et al.'s better spectral resolution measurements indicate that visibility is similar to the continuum beyond 60 km s⁻¹ from the line centre. An exponential is a better fit for the Br12 wings in this scenario. In comparison, the power-law fit has a low exponent of -1.3 ± 0.1 . The flat inner line core from Stark broadening, seen in Repolust et al. data and objects like BD+40°4124, is not here. A comparison of the strength of the line wings to peak intensity in the hydrogen recombination lines in the data reported here and in Drew et al. (1997) shows that the wings become stronger for lower n transitions in a reasonably uniform manner. This strongly suggests electron scattering. The fact that the wings and continuum appear to be equally visible in the Weigelt et al. data shows that this scattering happens at tiny scales. (Lumsden et.al 2012)focus on the scattering model for MWC 297 as it provides the strongest evidence of its presence.

Figure 6. The best-fitting Castor et al. (1970) model to MWC297.

The Castor et al. model's best fit shows a reduced $\chi^2 = 2$, indicating a somewhat asymmetric line. Figure 6 illustrates the fit for this source. The opacity of Thomson scattering exceeds unity, indicating that the model's criteria are not met. The implied electron temperature ($T_e \sim 170 \pm 10$ K) is low and not physically significant. The match of the Castor et al. profile in a case when the intrinsic line core is very small supports scattering as the major mechanism, however this model is insufficient to accurately estimate critical scattering-related physical parameters. Acke et al. (2008) failed to fit their combined near and mid-infrared interferometry to a pure accretion disc model, implying that more than one component was present.

Malbet et al. suggest a combination of disc and a weak outflowing wind can explain their near-infrared interferometry and the observed P-Cygni profile in Br γ . However, they struggle to find a good fit to the red wing of the Br γ line because their model predicts disc shadowing, which is not seen. The same is true of the models applied to the high spectral resolution observations of Weigelt et al. (2011) as well (which otherwise reach a very similar conclusion to Malbet et al). However, the rather obvious evidence of considerable dispersion in the line wings mitigates this issue. In a face-on orientation, the absence of a visible line effect in Oudmaijer & Drew's (1999) spectropolarimetry is not important because such a signature requires an asymmetry in the source structure as seen on the sky, which is not present. Weigelt et al. found evidence of a rotating signature in Br γ during the differential phase, which would not be present in a face-on condition. Acke et al. (2008) propose an intermediate inclination as a compromise to harmonize the available facts.

Conclusion

In summary, the intricate interplay of disk and wind processes in young group stars like MWC 297 underscores the dynamic evolution of stellar environments. As researchers demonstrate that the accretion dynamics associated with the protoplanetary disk play a critical role in shaping the mass and composition of these stars. Furthermore, the outflowing winds not only contribute to the removal of angular momentum but also affect the surrounding interstellar medium, thereby influencing subsequent star formation and the chemical enrichment of the galaxy. The evidence gathered from

observations and simulations suggests that these processes are not merely isolated phenomena; rather, they are interconnected components that drive the life cycles of young stars.

The high series infrared hydrogen lines' strong line broadening mechanisms have the significant side effect of making them poor tracers of a wind or a disk when used alone. A better tracer of a breeze are probably the He I lines from metastable levels, although, unfortunately, not every YSO shows this emission. However, by broadening, the hydrogen lines offer a way to check for the presence of extremely dense circumstellar material.

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